

Supplementary material to the paper “A multi-mode, multi-frequency dielectric elastomer actuator”

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S1 DEA static response

S1.1 Force-stroke response

We measured the force-stroke response of the DEA (DE membrane only, NBS excluded) using linear motor ANT-25LA by Aerotech and load-cell KD40s by MESysteme. We prescribed a sinusoidal displacement with amplitude of 10 mm and frequency of 0.2 Hz on the flat DE membrane, while at the same time applying a constant voltage v . The stabilised response of the DE at $v = 0$ and $v = 2.75$ kV is shown in Fig. S1. As expected, increasing the applied voltage causes a reduction in the elastic stresses acting on the DE (because of the Maxwell stress contribution) and, hence, a decrease in the slope of the force-stroke curve (i.e., the DEA stiffness). When the stroke is equal to zero (i.e., the flat configuration), the force is equal to zero, regardless of the applied voltage (i.e., the flat configuration is a singular configuration for the actuator). The DEA shows a hysteretical behavior, due to the DE material viscoelastic and pseudoplastic response.

Figure S1: Force-stroke response of the DEA membrane when no voltage is applied ($v = 0$) and in the presence of a voltage $v = 2.75$ kV.

S1.2 NBS design

The NBS used to provide the DEA with a mechanical axial pre-load has the shape shown in Fig. S2. The NBS consists in two perpendicular rectangular harmonic steel strips ($l_N = 32.2$ mm, $t_N = 2$ mm, and thickness of $50 \mu\text{m}$), which are mounted on a frame with radial dimension $l'_N = 31$ mm, and buckled out of plane due to the applied pre-compression ($h \simeq 4.5$ mm). The flat pre-stretched DEA and the buckled NBS are mounted on rigid frames concentrically and placed at a distance $d = 16.5$ mm from one another. A rigid spacer with length $l = 21.5$ mm is placed in between the the DEA and the NBS, hence loading the elements axially against each other.

The out-of-plane displacement x_D of the DEA and that of the NBS, x_N , (as defined in Fig. S2) in a generic configuration are related as follow:

$$x_D = \Delta - x_N, \text{ with } \Delta = h + l - d. \quad (\text{S1})$$

The force-stroke responses (namely, axial force vs x_D and x_N respectively) of the DEA and the NBS are overlapped in Fig. S3a (F_D and F_N denote the DEA and the NBS force respectively). In this representation, the intersection point between the NBS and the DEA force-stroke curves identifies the equilibrium configuration of the system at a given voltage and in the absence of external applied mechanical loads. It is worth noticing that the intersection points fall within a region where the NBS has negative stiffness (i.e., the slope of the tensile curve is negative, on an $F_N - x_N$ diagram). This allows achieving larger voltage-induced strokes, compared to those that would have been achieved if a positive-stiffness elastic element were used, as graphically illustrated in Fig. S3b.

Figure S2: Schematic of the assembly steps of the NBS and the DEA: the NBS is initially precompressed radially and buckles out of plane (left). The pre-stretched NBS and DEA are aligned coaxially, at a given axial distance from one another (middle). A rigid spacer is used to bias the DEA out-of-plane against the NBS (right).

Figure S3: **a.** DEA and NBS force-stroke responses. The intersection points between the DEA and the NBS curves represent the equilibrium configurations for the system. **b.** Qualitative representation of the force-stroke curves of a DEA with linear biasing spring (top) or NBS (bottom). The maximum DEA stroke (distance between the intersection points at different voltages) is larger in the presence of a negative-stiffness NBS.

S2 Model of the DEA dynamic response

S2.1 Finite element model of the DEA acoustic response

Whereas models of the quasi-static or low-frequency pumping behaviour of DEAs with the conical layout have been largely validated in the past, only a few studies have focused on predicting the high-frequency acoustic response of these systems. In our previous paper [1], we presented a finite element model for the vibro-acoustic response of conical DEAs. The model relies on the assumption that the DE can be treated as a thin membrane (with no bending stiffness), whose stress-stretch response can be described in terms of an energy function that is the sum of a hyperelastic and an electrostatic contribution. The DE membrane model is bi-directionally coupled with a model of the surrounding acoustic domain (modelled as a spherical volume surrounding the DE and its holding frame), which, in dynamic operating conditions, is subject to a sound pressure field generated by the DE vibrations. This sound pressure field, in turns, influences the dynamics of the DE by inducing pressure loads on the membrane surface. Both the membrane and the surrounding acoustic domains are modelled as axial-symmetrical, since the dynamics of the system is dominated axial-symmetrical modes [2], whereas non-symmetrical modes observed in experiments are excited only as a consequence of second-order asymmetries or inhomogeneities present in the system. The model presented in [1] allows predicting the SPL generated by the DE membrane via a two-step computation: 1) first, a quasi static pre-loading (a constant bias voltage and an off-plane deformation) is applied on the DE; 2) then, a frequency-domain analysis of the system response is performed, assuming that the DE is subject to a constant-amplitude voltage excitation. For the second step, the DEA dynamics are linearized above the equilibrium configuration (bias voltage and off-plane deformation). The output of the second computation step is the distribution of the SPL in the domain surrounding the DE.

The model is implemented in the software Comsol Multiphysics, making use of the in-built Nonlinear Structural Mechanics and Acoustic modules, and implementing user-defined functions to consistently describe the electro-acoustic interactions (i.e., the contribution of the voltage in the energy density function). Consistent coupling between the membrane and the acoustic domain is implemented by means of a moving mesh feature. Further details on the models assumptions and implementation are discussed in [1].

Model assumptions		
Hyperelastic params.	$c_{1,0}$	194 kPa
(3-param. Mooney-Rivlin)	$c_{2,0}$	71 kPa
	$c_{0,1}$	-24 kPa
Dielectric permittivity	ε	$2.8 \cdot 8.9 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m
Structural damping loss fact.	η_s	0.15
DE density	ρ	1400 kg/m ³

Table 1: Material parameters used in the simulation

We used the described model to predict the acoustic response of the DEA investigated in this work. Similar to [1], we used the material parameters listed in Tab. 1. In particular, we described the DE elastic response via a generalised Mooney-Rivlin hyperelastic model, the visco-elastic response via a structural damping (with loss factor η_s). We assumed the thickness of the membrane be equal to the total thickness of the dielectric layers, and chose a suitable value for the density (higher than the density of the dielectric) so as to account for the contribution of the screen-printed electrodes on the total DE mass. The geometry of the structure surrounding the DEA was modelled in a simplified way as a thin flat square panel with 80 mm side length. Although this geometry represents a drastic simplification compared to the actual structure, it accounts for sound reflections from the walls around the DE, while still keeping into account acoustic short circuit effects between the front and the back of the membrane (as the box holding the DE is not laterally sealed). The air volume surrounding the sample has been modelled as a spherical

volume with a radius of 450 mm, surrounded by a permanently matched layer with thickness equal to the membrane outer radius. Other details on the model and its implementation are provided in [1].

The plots in Fig. S4 compare the experimental trends of the SPL (as a function of the frequency) with the model's predictions. In the simulations, the OD of the device is held fixed, and the resulting predictions are compared with the SPL measurements obtained in the two blocking tests presented in Fig. 2b in the paper, which feature different bias voltage and out-of-plane deformation, namely: B1: $V_b = 1$ kV, $h_0 = 5.1$ mm; B2: $V_b = 2$ kV, $h_0 = 5.6$ mm. In both tests, the applied voltage has an amplitude $V_a = 100$ V.

Figure S4: SPL in blocking conditions (B1 and B2, as defined in Fig. 2b in the paper): comparison of experimental data and finite element model predictions. The green bands indicate the range where the natural frequencies of the corresponding modes (whose value is different in the two cases) are comprised.

The model captures the global qualitative and quantitative trend of the SPL in the considered frequency range. In particular, the model predicts the location and magnitude of the peak associated to the first structural mode (mode (0,1)), in the neighborhood of which the SPL rises from 40 dB to 75-85 dB (depending on the biasing voltage). The model shows that, in the considered frequency range, the membrane features at least 4 axial-symmetrical modes (from (0,1) to (0,4)). In particular, the acoustic response shows peaks (with an increase in the sound pressure level consistent with the experimental data) in correspondence modes (0,1) and (0,3), whereas modes (0,2) and (0,4) (with an even number of antinodes) have a minor influence on the acoustic response. In addition to that, the model is able to explain the variation in SPL generated by different electro-mechanical biasing conditions.

As already discussed in [1], because of the drastic simplifications used here to describe the material damping, the model does not entirely capture some features of the acoustic response (e.g., the presence of antiresonances in the acoustic response in the range 4-4.5 kHz), and in particular it tends to overestimate the amount of damping present in the response at the highest frequencies. To improve the model accuracy, one should resort to a more complex damping model (e.g., a rheological visco-elastic model), for which a specific characterization would be required. The model, in the form presented here and in [1], still allows obtaining a reliable estimate of the generated SPL and its dependency on the design parameters.

Figure S5: Cone DEA in the initial (reference) configuration and in a generic deformed configuration

S2.2 Nonlinear dynamics

The finite element model presented in Sect. S2 allows solving the linearised continuum dynamics of the DEA in the neighbourhood of a given working configuration and estimate the associated acoustic frequency response. The response of the system to multi-frequency excitations, however, shows trends that can only be explained in terms of nonlinear system's dynamics (namely, the beat distortions shown in Fig. 3). With the aim of qualitatively explaining the origins of these effects, we hereby resort to a lumped-parameter formulation, based on a mode described and validated in [2, 3], and shortly recalled in the following.

The lumped-parameter model discussed here relies on a modal approach: we use a set of mode shape functions (namely, the modal eigenfunctions) to parameterise the deformed DEA geometry via a finite number of degrees of freedom, and we express the total DEA deformation as a finite linear superposition of mode shapes. Each mode shapes describes the DEA displacements associated to a certain free vibration mode. This modal approach is largely used in the analysis of dynamical systems, and it has been applied to DE loudspeakers in the past [2–4].

Denoting \mathbf{X} the position of a generic point over the DE surface (in a reference configuration, e.g., the equilibrium DEA position, prior to voltage application), the displacement field \mathbf{u} of a generic point of the DEA (Fig. S5) with respect to the reference configuration can be thus approximated as follows:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{X}) = \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{X})\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{X}) : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{3 \times n}$ is a multivariate function whose elements describe the mode shapes of the DEA, and $\boldsymbol{\alpha} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a modal coordinate whose dimension, n , equals the number of the considered eigenmodes. We define $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ in such a way that $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \mathbf{0}$ denotes the initial configuration.

The DEA dynamics can be expressed in terms of modal coordinate $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$ leading to the following n -dimensional equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}\ddot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \mathbf{D}\dot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}} + \mathbf{K}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) &= \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})v^2, \text{ with} \\ \mathbf{K}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) &= \frac{\partial U(\boldsymbol{\alpha})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\alpha}}, \quad \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial C(\boldsymbol{\alpha})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\alpha}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3})$$

$\mathbf{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are modal mass and damping matrices of appropriate dimensions. $\mathbf{K}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a vector function of non-linear modal elastic forces, which depend on the elastic potential energy of the system $U(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ (i.e., the sum of the DE membrane elastic energy, typically expressed via a hyperelastic model, and the elastic energy of the NBS). Finally, excitation coefficient $\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is proportional to the gradient of the capacitance $C(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$ (notice that $U(\boldsymbol{\alpha}), C(\boldsymbol{\alpha}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$).

A formulation for the calculation of the DEA eigenmodes and the single terms in (S3) is discussed in [2], with reference to the case of purely axial-symmetrical deformations. In particular, the eigenmodes $\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{X})$ are calculated by linearising the DEA dynamics in the neighbourhood of a given configuration. Despite this, dynamics (S3) are still non-linear, as the eigenmodes here are just used as a mean of parametrising the DEA deformation kinematics in a finite-dimensional fashion (i.e., the eigenmodes, obtained from

system linearisation, are here just used to perform a change of coordinates, resulting in reduction of the problem dimension).

As regards the dynamics parameters, it is worth noticing that, in addition to the inertia of the DE membrane and the OD, the mass matrix \mathbf{M} shall include contributions due to the acoustic added mass, i.e., the air of mass put into motion by the membrane vibration. This contribution plays a relevant role in the structural vibrations of thin lightweight membranes. Similarly, damping \mathbf{D} accounts for both the viscous stresses in the DE membrane and the acoustic damping (i.e., the energy lost as sound radiation).

Based on Eq. (S3), the voltage enters the equations of motion through an excitation term (right-hand side of the equation) proportional to v^2 , rendering the contribution of the Maxwell stress.

According to Rayleigh theory [5], the acoustic pressure p generated by the DEA at a target point in space is linearly related to the dynamic response by a relationship in the following general form:

$$p = \int_0^t \mathbf{H}^T(t - \tau) \ddot{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(\tau) d\tau, \quad (\text{S4})$$

where $\mathbf{H}(t) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is a suitably defined kernel vector function, which only depends on the geometry of the membrane and the surrounding environment, and the location of the receptor point.

In [2], we validated model (S3) against laser vibrometer measurements. In [3], we used Eqs. (S3)-(S4) to build a linear-parameter varying model of the system, able to predict the acoustic response in the presence of a slowly-varying bias voltage superposed to a HF excitation.

S2.3 Multi-frequency input and distortions

Driving the DEA with a multi-frequency input given by the superposition of a LF signal (with frequency f_L) and a HF signal (with frequency f_H) leads to distortions in the acoustic response (see Fig. 3), namely, the sound level decreases periodically (low-frequency modulation) with a period equal to $1/f_L$. In terms of the sound spectra, this can be interpreted as a beat pattern.

With reference to the experiment discussed in Fig. 3a (free oscillating DEA driven by a multi-frequency input), Fig. S6a shows the time-series of the generated sound pressure, whereas Fig. S6b shows its spectrum (calculated using the fast Fourier-transform algorithm). In addition to the fundamental component (at frequency f_H), the spectrum includes higher-frequency terms which are multiples of the fundamental ($2f_H, 3f_H, \dots$), which result in harmonic distortions of the output (i.e., distortions within the periodic response at frequency f_H). Most importantly, the spectrum includes harmonic components which are close to the fundamental frequency, and only differ by f_L (or its multiples). As it is well-known, the superposition of the fundamental with such neighboring harmonics results in a beat pattern, which is ultimately responsible for the time-trend of the sound pressure shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. S6a

The reason why the DEA response includes these higher-order harmonics can be qualitatively explained using model (S3)-(S4). For the simple purpose of justifying the beat distortion shown in Fig. S6, we introduce the following assumptions:

- The input v^2 is the sum of two terms (a LF term \bar{u} , and a HF term \tilde{u}), assumed sinusoidal for simplicity:

$$v^2 = \bar{u} + \tilde{u}, \text{ where } \bar{u} = U_0 + U_1 \sin(2\pi f_L t), \tilde{u} = U_2 \sin(2\pi f_H t + \phi), \quad (\text{S5})$$

and the amplitude of \tilde{u} is much smaller than that of \bar{u} : $|\tilde{u}(t)| \ll |\bar{u}(t)| \forall t$. As a consequence, the membrane deformation too can be expressed as the sum of two components, as discussed in [3], namely:

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}(t) = \bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(t) + \tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(t), \text{ with } |\tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(t)| \ll |\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(t)|. \quad (\text{S6})$$

We call $\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}$ the solution to Eq. (S3) obtained for $v^2 = \bar{u}$, namely

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}} + \mathbf{D}\dot{\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}} + \mathbf{K}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}) = \mathbf{h}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\alpha}})\bar{u}, \quad (\text{S7})$$

whereas $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}$ is an additional deformation appearing when the DEA is driven by input (S5).

Figure S6: Time series (a.) and spectrum (b.) of the sound pressure for the test shown in Fig. 3a in the main paper. In the test, the DEA is subject to a multi frequency input (both the HF and the LF component have sinusoidal waveform and constant amplitude)

- Multi-frequency input (S5) only excites two vibration modes ($n = 2$): the pumping mode and a structural mode, while the contribution of other modes in the dynamics is neglected. Moreover, since the passband of the pumping mode is well-resolved from those of the structural modes, we assume that \bar{u} only excites the pumping mode, whereas \tilde{u} only excites the structural mode, namely:

$$\bar{\alpha} = [\bar{\alpha} \ 0]^T, \quad \tilde{\alpha} = [0 \ \tilde{\alpha}]^T, \quad (\text{S8})$$

where $\bar{\alpha}$ and $\tilde{\alpha}$ are parameters describing the dynamics of the individual modes.

We linearize Eq. (S3) around trajectory $\bar{\alpha}$, i.e., the pumping mode, and using Eq. (S7) we obtain the following dynamics for $\tilde{\alpha}$, i.e., the excited structural mode:

$$M\ddot{\tilde{\alpha}} + \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}(\bar{\alpha})}{\partial \alpha} - \bar{u} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}(\bar{\alpha})}{\partial \alpha} \right] \tilde{\alpha} = \mathbf{h}(\bar{\alpha})\tilde{u}. \quad (\text{S9})$$

Eq. (S9) is linear with respect to \tilde{u} and $\tilde{\alpha}$, with coefficients (namely, the stiffness and the excitation coefficient) that vary in time in a parametric fashion, as functions of the slow dynamics (namely, of \bar{u} and $\bar{\alpha}$).

We focus on the dynamics of $\tilde{\alpha}$ (as this is the main responsible for the sound generation), and thus restrict ourselves to consider the second component of Eq. (S9). For the purpose of exemplification, we assume that $\partial K_{22}(\alpha)/\partial \alpha_2$ and $h_2(\alpha)$ (components of $\partial \mathbf{K}(\alpha)/\partial \alpha$ and $\mathbf{h}(\alpha)$) can be approximated by linear functions, and configuration-induced variations (i.e., dependency on $\bar{\alpha}$) in the stiffness and the excitation are small:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial K_{22}(\alpha)}{\partial \alpha_2} &= k + k'\bar{\alpha}, \quad h_2(\alpha) = h + h'\bar{\alpha}, \quad \text{for } \alpha = \bar{\alpha} = [\bar{\alpha} \ 0]^T \\ \text{with } |k'\bar{\alpha}| &\ll |k|, \quad |h'\bar{\alpha}| \ll |h| \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S10})$$

where k , k' , h , h' are constant coefficients.

Replacing (S10) into the second component of (S9) leads to the following dynamics for $\tilde{\alpha}$:

$$M_{22}\ddot{\tilde{\alpha}}(t) + [k + k'\bar{\alpha}(t) - h'\bar{u}(t)] \tilde{\alpha}(t) = [h + h'\bar{\alpha}(t)]\tilde{u}(t). \quad (\text{S11})$$

Because the timescale over which \bar{u} and $\bar{\alpha}$ vary is much longer than the timescale of the variations in \tilde{u} and $\tilde{\alpha}$, we can provide an approximate solution to (S11) by treating the terms into square brackets as

constants, and re-introducing the dependency of \bar{u} and $\bar{\alpha}$ on time after the equation has been solved. This leads to the following solution:

$$\tilde{\alpha}(t) \simeq \frac{[h + h'\bar{\alpha}(t)] \tilde{u}(t)}{-\omega_H^2 M_{22} + k + k'\bar{\alpha}(t) - h'\tilde{u}(t)} \simeq \left[h + h'\bar{\alpha}(t) + h \frac{h'\tilde{u}(t) - k'\bar{\alpha}(t)}{k - \omega_H^2 M_{22}} \right] \frac{\tilde{u}(t)}{k - \omega_H^2 M_{22}} \quad (\text{S12})$$

In the right-hand side of (S12), we assumed that (S10) holds, and that voltage-induced stiffness variations of the DE are small ($|h'\tilde{u}(t)| \ll k$), and we neglected second order terms accordingly.

In Eq. (S12), \bar{u} and $\tilde{u}(t)$ are sine waves with frequency of f_L and f_H (Eq. (S5)), whereas $\bar{\alpha}(t)$ is a periodic signal with fundamental frequency f_L (plus possible additional multiple harmonics). The time-trend of $\tilde{\alpha}(t)$ thus contains a fundamental harmonic term proportional to \tilde{u} , plus a set of second-order terms which are proportional to the products $\bar{u}\tilde{u}$ and $\bar{\alpha}\tilde{u}$, and they hence lead to additional harmonic terms with frequency $f_H + f_L$ and $f_H - f_L$ (plus similar terms where the integer multiples of f_L appear). Given that the transfer function between the accelerations and the sound pressure is linear (Eq. (S4)), this consistently explains the beat harmonics observed in the sound spectrum in Fig. (S6)b.

It is finally worth noticing that the modelling approach presented here and in [3] provides a possible tool to design advanced control strategies to equalise the DEA acoustic response in the presence of multi-frequency inputs, via model-based filtering.

Figure S7: Picture of the acoustic box used for the experiments, the vibrometer laser heads, and the DEA sample and microphone installed inside the box.

S3 Experimental setup

S3.1 Acoustic test-bench

During the tests, the DEA was installed in a custom-built acoustic box with sound absorbing walls (see Fig. S7). The envelope size of the box is $110 \times 100 \times 80$ cm. The external walls are made of 12mm-thick plywood. The internal walls are covered with a double layer of foam: 60 mm closed-cell polyethylene foam, and 50 mm polyester fibre, which provides sound absorption of the incident sound (estimated absorption: $> 80\%$) in a broad frequency range ($f > 300$ Hz). The box's floor is covered with re-configurable foam tiles, which allow different relative positions of the speakers/microphones.

Measurements of the velocity spectra and the DEA's OD displacement were carried out using a laser vibrometer (PSV-500 3D by Polytec). The laser heads of the vibrometer are installed in front of the

sound absorbing box. To allow simultaneous measurements of the acoustic and the vibratory response, an aperture (48×51 cm) was left open on the box front wall during the tests. The measurement microphone was located inside the box, and aligned with the DEA sample axis.

For the purpose of reconstructing the DEA average velocity spectra (Fig. S8), measurements were taken at 68 different points over the DEA surface. The grid of the measured points is shown in Fig. S8. Average spectra were calculated as the arithmetic mean of the spectra in the single points, using the vibrometer proprietary software.

Figure S8: Frontal view of the DEA samples from the vibrometer software (PSV9.1), showing the grid of points used to calculate the average velocity spectra.

S3.2 Driving circuit

For the tests in Figs. 3-5, the DEA was simply connected in parallel to the high-voltage amplifier (Trek 609E-6), the input waveform for the amplifier was generated with the analog outputs of data acquisition electronics, and voltage/current measurements were obtained from the amplifier's analog monitors.

For the acoustic tests in Fig. 6 and Video 3, an additional custom-built current sensor was connected in series to the DEA (on the ground side), as shown in Fig. S9, and a microcontroller (STM32 H743ZI2) was used to implement the sensing logics and generate the driving waveforms. Compared to the Trek's monitor, this sensor has a resolution 100 time higher (range of $200 \mu\text{A}$ vs. 20 mA). Measurements from the external current sensor have been used to recognise users' touch and trig the DEA response via a microcontroller (STM32 H743ZI2, programmed in C). Because during the execution of the DEA routing the external sensor reaches its saturation limit, the current plot in Fig. 6b comes from the amplifier's monitor.

Figure S9: Circuit layout used for the audio-tactile proof-of-concept in sect. 2.2. A high-resolution current sensor is connected in series to the DEA and used to detect peaks in the current, which are in turn used to control the DEA driving voltage.

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